

Synthesis and characterization of high curie temperature piezoelectric ceramics

BaTiNb₂O₈

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Abstract

In recent years, there has been continued interest in high Curie temperature piezoelectric ceramics due to their stability in harsh environment applications such as aerospace and geological exploration. We present the x-ray diffraction, dielectric measurements and polarization-electric field hysteresis studies on new high Curie temperature piezoelectric BaTiNb₂O₈ ceramic synthesized by solid state route. The Powder x-ray diffraction reveals that the compound BaTiNb₂O₈ shows triclinic structure with space group P1. BTNO ceramic shows ferroelectric phase transition at very high Curie temperature $T_c = 468$ °C.

“Keywords: X-ray diffraction; Piezoelectric; Dielectric; SEM; EDS”.

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